

ABSTRACT

Cellulases attract a lot of research due to their industrial application. Diverse cellulase-producing organisms and substances that induce cellulase are highly sought after. The current study is concerned with the kinetics and biochemical characterization of cellulase from a yeast strain, *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 1090. Carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) was used as substrate to produce and optimize cellulase from the yeast. The effect of various fermentation conditions for cellulase production through solid-state fermentation was investigated. Maximum enzyme production was obtained after 24 h of incubation in fermentation medium. The maximum cellulase was produced at pH 5.0. Meat extract was the best nitrogen source for optimum cellulase production. Purification of the crude enzyme was done by gel filtration using Sephadex G-200. Specific activity after purification increased from 294.5 to 1141.3 U/mg, and the protein content dropped from 0.66 to 0.23 mg/mL with 59% yield and 2 folds. Cellulase characterization revealed that optimum activity was at pH 4.5 and temperature of 70 °C. Maximal activity of the enzyme was obtained at substrate concentration of 0.5 mg/mL. Kinetic analysis of the partially purified enzyme gave V_{max} , of 188.6792 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}$ and a Michaelis-Menten constant, K_m , of 0.018868 mg cellulase, respectively. This study reveals the suitability of obtaining cheap source of cellulase from a fungal isolate, which can have potential applications in biotechnological and other related industries.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

The background of study on cellulase production and its applications is rooted in the need to develop efficient and cost-effective methods for the degradation of cellulose, a complex carbohydrate found in plant cell walls. Cellulose is the most abundant organic compound on Earth, making up approximately 50% of plant biomass. It is a key component of plant cell walls and serves as a structural framework, providing strength and rigidity to the plant. The degradation of cellulose is crucial for various industrial processes, including biofuel production, biorefineries, and paper manufacturing. Cellulase is an enzyme that hydrolyzes cellulose, breaking down the complex carbohydrate into simple sugars such as glucose, xylose, and arabinose. It is produced primarily by fungi, bacteria, and protozoans and is involved in the decomposition of cellulose and related polysaccharides. Cellulases are used in various industries, including textiles, food, biofuels, and biorefineries, where they play a crucial role in processes such as fabric softening, juice clarification, and biomass conversion (Ejaz et al., 2021). In addition, cellulase is used in detergent production to enhance fabric smoothness and soil removal without damage, contributing to environmentally friendly cleaning practices. Studies focus on enzyme production, optimization strategies and structural characteristics, aiming to enhance efficiency and stability. Research explores cellulase production by microorganisms like *Bacillus subtilis* and *Trichoderma reesei*, emphasizing real-time visualization methods for cellulase activity (Kumari et al., 2020). Techniques include partial purification, characterization, and quantification of cellulase activity. Overall, the study aims to contribute to the advancement of

cellulase production processes, enhancing their efficiency and cost-effectiveness for various industrial applications, particularly in the production of biofuels from lignocellulosic biomass.

1.1 Overview of Cellulase

Cellulase is a complex enzyme with a multi-domain structure, typically consisting of a catalytic domain and a cellulose binding domain connected by a flexible linker. The catalytic domain is responsible for breaking down cellulose into simple sugars, while the cellulose binding domain helps in the attachment and anchoring of the enzyme to the cellulose substrate. The catalytic domain of cellulase is composed of eight β -sheets surrounded by eight α -helices, forming a canonical (β/α) 8-barrel fold. Two acidic residues, Glu 240 and Glu 152, are identified as the catalytic acidic residues, which are responsible for the hydrolysis of cellulose (Ejaz et al., 2021). The crystal structure of a novel halotolerant cellulase, Cel5R, determined at 2.2 Å resolution reveals a large number of acidic residues on the surface of the enzyme, contributing to its halotolerance and thermal stability (Garg et al., 2016).

Figure 1.1 Structure of cellulase (2024).

1.1.1 Sources of cellulase

Cellulase is produced by various microorganisms, including bacteria and fungi. Bacteria are prolific producers of cellulases, as they secrete these enzymes in abundant amounts, making them easier to extract. Some bacteria known for cellulase production include *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus halodurans*, *B. subtilis* BC1, *B. subtilis* BY-4, and *B. subtilis* CD001 (Malik et al., 2021). Cellulose is a major component of plant cell walls, and cellulose-degrading bacteria are found in soil, where they play a crucial role in the decomposition of cellulose (Sethi et al., 2013). Fungi, particularly *Trichoderma* species, are also a preferred source for cellulase production, especially in the Pulp and Paper industry. In textiles, cellulases soften cotton and finish denim. In laundry detergents, they aid in color care, cleaning, and anti-deposition. The food industry

utilizes cellulase for mashing, while the pulp and paper sector employs it for drinking, drainage improvement, and fiber modification (Globe News Wire, 2023). Cellulase production can be influenced by various factors, such as carbon sources, nitrogen sources, and temperature. For example, carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) has been reported as the best carbon source for inducing extracellular cellulase production in *B. subtilis* CD001 (Malik et al., 2021). The optimum conditions for cellulase production are 40 °C at pH 10 with glucose as the carbon source and ammonium sulfate and coconut cake as nitrogen sources (Sethi et al., 2013)

Figure 1.2: Sources of cellulolytic/xylanolytic enzymes (2020).

1.1.2 Methods of extracting cellulase from bacteria and fungi

Cellulase can be extracted from bacteria and fungi using several methods. For bacteria, the process typically involves the following steps:

1. Isolation of cellulase-producing bacteria: This can be done by screening waste materials, such as molasses, for bacteria that can produce cellulase (Islam et al., 2018).
2. Optimization of culture conditions: The optimal conditions for cellulase production can vary depending on the bacterial strain. Factors such as pH, temperature, incubation period, substrate concentration, and carbon sources can be optimized to maximize enzyme production (Islam et al., 2018).
3. Crude cellulase extraction: The crude cellulase can be extracted from the bacterial culture by centrifugation or filtration (Islam et al., 2018).
4. Purification of cellulase: The crude cellulase can be purified using techniques such as ammonium sulfate precipitation, DEAE-cellulose column chromatography, and CM-cellulose column chromatography (Islam et al., 2018).

For fungi, the process typically involves the following steps:

1. Isolation of cellulase-producing fungi: This can be done by screening various fungal strains for their ability to produce cellulase (Sajith et al., 2014).
2. Optimization of culture conditions: The optimal conditions for cellulase production can vary depending on the fungal strain. Factors such as pH, temperature, incubation period, substrate concentration, and carbon sources can be optimized to maximize enzyme production (Sajith *et al.*, 2014).

3. Crude cellulase extraction: The crude cellulase can be extracted from the fungal culture by centrifugation or filtration (Sajith et al., 2014).

4. Purification of cellulase: The crude cellulase can be purified using techniques such as centrifugation, ultrafiltration, and chromatography methods (Sajith et al., 2014).

The choice of extraction and purification methods depends on the specific bacterial or fungal strain being used, as well as the desired purity and yield of the cellulase enzyme.

1.1.3 Types of cellulase

Cellulase enzymes are classified into three main types based on their mode of action and structure: endoglucanases, exocellulases, and processive endoglucanases.

1. Endoglucanases: These enzymes act by cleaving internal β -1,4-glycosidic bonds within cellulose chains, initiating the degradation process. Endoglucanases are crucial for breaking down cellulose into smaller fragments, facilitating further hydrolysis by other cellulases. They are known for their ability to randomly attack cellulose chains, creating new chain ends for other enzymes to act upon.

2. Exocellulases: Exocellulases work by attacking the ends of cellulose chains, either the reducing ends or the non-reducing ends. Exocellulases cleave cellobiose residues sequentially from the end of a cellulose molecule. There are two classes of exocellulases: one class targets the reducing ends of cellulose chains, found in families GH-7 or GH-48, while the other class targets the non-reducing ends, present in family GH-6. Exocellulases have active sites in a tunnel, enabling their processive activity (Wilson et al., 2012).

3. Processive Endoglucanases: These cellulases exhibit processivity, meaning they can interact with a single polysaccharide strand continuously without disengaging. Processive endoglucanases include enzymes like GH-9 and GH-5 catalytic domains with specific carbohydrate binding modules (CBMs) that aid in their processive action. The family 3c CBM is essential for the processivity of some endoglucanases, ensuring efficient degradation of cellulose chains (Wilson et al., 2012).

1.1.4 Production of cellulase

The production of cellulase involves optimizing various parameters to maximize enzyme yield. Factors such as temperature, pH, substrate concentration, and incubation time play crucial roles in cellulase production. The optimal conditions for cellulase production are 50 °C, pH 5.5, and an incubation time of 72 h. Cellulase production can be enhanced by using cost-effective carbon sources like cheese whey, bagasse, rice straw, and lignocellulosic materials, which induce cellulase production efficiently. Solid-state fermentation (SSF) has gained popularity due to its cost-effectiveness and suitability for bioconversion, making it a favorable method for cellulase production from agro-industrial wastes (Alan et al., 2024).

The microorganisms that appear to be most promising at present for cellulase production are *Aspergillus* sp. and *Trichoderma* sp. However, it is of interest to examine *Aspergillus* sp. to improve cellulase production, which is a known good producer of cellulases (Chavda et al., 2023). Many researches have been conducted on enzymatic hydrolysis of various lignocellulolytic substrates like pumpkin oil cake, sawdust, pineapple waste, orange waste, palm oil mill effluent, pea shrub biomass, sugarcane bagasse, rice bran, rice straw, wheat bran, vinegar waste, cassava waste, corn straw, wheat straw, rice husk, soybean, cotton, corn cob, green grass, dried grass, millet, oats straw, oil palm biomass, banana stalk, mulch, radicle waste, sago

hampas, grape wine, cutting waste, steam pretreated willow, sweet sorghum silage, paddy straw, coconut coir pith, and many more. These studies have shown that various lignocellulosic substrates can be used as carbon sources for cellulase production (Praveen et al., 2015).

1.1.4.1 Solid-State Fermentation

Solid-state fermentation (SSF) is a fermentation process where microorganisms grow on solid materials in the absence of free liquid. It is utilized in various industries like pharmaceuticals, food, and textiles to produce metabolites of microorganisms using solid support instead of a liquid medium. SSF involves the growth of organisms on solid substrates with low moisture levels, such as cereal grains, legume seeds, lignocellulose materials, and other plant and animal materials. This method is an alternative to submerged fermentation and is used for producing a range of valuable products like antibiotics, enzymes, organic acids, bio-pesticides, and biofuels. SSF offers advantages over submerged fermentation, making it a versatile and efficient process for biotechnological applications (Nicolás et al., 2022).

The advantages of solid-state fermentation (SSF) for cellulase production include simplicity, low capital investment, low energy requirements, and the ability to use inexpensive substrates (Rodriguez-Couto et al., 2006). SSF eliminates the need for solubilizing nutrients from solid substrates, requires less rigorous control of fermentation parameters, often results in higher product yields, has lower energy requirements, produces less wastewater, does not generate foam, and allows for relatively easy recovery of end products (Manan et al., 2017).

On the other hand, SSF has some disadvantages, including challenges related to temperature build-up, uneven distribution of cell mass, nutrients, temperature, pH, and moisture content, difficulties in achieving steady aeration throughout the substrate, heat generated from microbial

metabolism raising substrate temperature, limitations in biomass measurement for microbial growth, and the complexity of growth and kinetics studies. These challenges can impact the efficiency and control of the fermentation process in SSF (Lizardi-Jiménez et al., 2017).

1.1.4.2 Fermentation process of cellulase production

Cellulase fermentation is a process used to produce cellulases, which are essential for breaking down cellulose into simpler sugars that can be used as a source of energy and other valuable products. The fermentation process involves the use of microorganisms, such as bacteria or fungi, that are capable of producing cellulases.

One study conducted cellulase fermentation using a high-titer enzyme-producing strain CDU-11 under semi-batch conditions in a 4-L fermentor, using inexpensive carbon and nitrogen sources and the pH-shift system. This resulted in the production of CMCase activity exceeding 600 U/mL and (3-glucosidase activity exceeding 30 U/mL) (Ye et al., 2017). Another study used *Trichoderma* and *Aspergillus* species to produce cellulases through solid-state fermentation (SSF) utilizing banana pseudostem (BPS) as a carbon source. The study found that the use of BPS as a substrate resulted in high cellulase productivity (Lesetja et al., 2023). Cellulase fermentation can also be conducted on a novel substrate, such as waste cardboard. One study found that cellulases have a positive effect on the caecal fermentation processes by increasing the production of propionic acid, which acts as a bacteriostatic material (Nóra et al., 2004). The highest cellulase production is reported using *Trichoderma* as inoculum and agro-industrial wastes as substrates, with activity production ranging between one and hundreds depending on the operational conditions. For instance, when cellulose content of the substrate is below 30%, low cellulase productivities are obtained (below 3FPU g⁻¹DM), proving that cellulase production is highly induced by cellulose (Cerdeira et al., 2019).

1.1.5 Purification of cellulase

Cellulase purification involves several steps to isolate and concentrate the enzyme for various applications. The process typically includes ammonium sulfate precipitation, gel-filtration chromatography, ion exchange chromatography, and gel filtration on Sephadex G-200. For example, in one study, cellulase was purified through ammonium sulfate precipitation, gel-filtration chromatography, and ion exchange chromatography, resulting in a 39.1-fold purification factor and a final recovery of 28.8% of the enzyme (Gaur et al., 2015). The purification process aims to remove impurities and concentrate the cellulase, ensuring its effectiveness in industrial applications. Additionally, the purity of the enzyme is confirmed through techniques like SDS-PAGE, which shows a single band indicating the presence of the purified enzyme. Overall, cellulase purification involves a series of precise steps to obtain a highly concentrated and pure enzyme for efficient use in various industries (Elsababty et al., 2022).

1.1.5.1 Chromatographic methods for cellulase purification

Chromatography is a common method used for the purification of cellulases. The choice of chromatographic method depends on the specific properties of the cellulase and the desired level of purity.

Ion-exchange chromatography is a method that separates cellulases based on their charge. It involves the use of a resin with positively or negatively charged functional groups that bind to the enzymes based on their charge. The bound enzymes are then eluted using a buffer with a different pH or ionic strength. This method is useful for separating cellulases with different

isoelectric points (pI) or charge densities (Sulyman et al., 2020). Gel filtration chromatography, also known as size-exclusion chromatography, separates cellulases based on their size and molecular weight. It involves the use of a column packed with porous beads that allow smaller molecules to penetrate deeper into the beads, resulting in longer retention times. This method is useful for separating cellulases with different molecular weights or sizes (Noor et al., 2018). Gel filtration chromatography is often used as a final step to purify the enzyme for further use. For example, one study used gel filtration chromatography as the final step in the purification of cellulase produced by a mutant isolate of *Trichoderma longibrachiatum* (Noor et al., 2018). The enzyme was eluted from the column in the elution fractions and further purified using the gel filtration chromatography technique to purify the enzyme for further enzyme assays (Sulyman et al., 2020). The advantages of gel filtration chromatography include its ability to separate molecules solely based on size, making it particularly useful for separating cellulases with different molecular weights or sizes. However, the technique also has some disadvantages, such as the need for large volumes of eluent, which can create excessive running costs, and a low resolution compared with other chromatographic techniques (O'Fágáin et al., 2011).

Affinity chromatography is a method that separates cellulases based on their specific binding to a ligand. It involves the use of a resin with a ligand that specifically binds to the enzyme of interest. The bound enzymes are then eluted using a buffer that disrupts the binding between the enzyme and the ligand. This method is useful for purifying cellulases with specific activities or functions (Megha et al., 2015).

1.2 Factors affecting enzyme production

1.2.1 Effect of nitrogen sources on enzyme production

The effect of nitrogen sources on enzyme production is a widely studied topic in the field of biotechnology. Nitrogen is an essential nutrient for microbial growth and enzyme production, and the type and concentration of nitrogen source can significantly affect enzyme activity. Studies have shown that different nitrogen sources can have varying effects on enzyme production. For example, ammonium sulfate and urea were reported as the best nitrogen sources for the production of lignocellulolytic enzymes by the fungus *Phanerochaete chrysosporium*, while peptone and yeast extract were less effective (Sevakumaran et al., 2015). Another study had it that ammonium nitrate and ammonium sulfate were the best nitrogen sources for the production of cellulase enzymes by the fungus *Trichoderma reesei*, while yeast extract and peptone were less effective (Kachlishvili et al., 2006).

The concentration of nitrogen source can also affect enzyme production. It was reported that the optimal concentration of ammonium sulfate for the production of cellulases by the fungus *Trichoderma reesei* was 0.5% (w/v), while higher concentrations inhibited enzyme production (do Nascimento et al., 2019). Another study found that the optimal concentration of ammonium nitrate for the production of xylanases by the fungus *Aspergillus niger* was 1.5% (w/v), while higher concentrations inhibited enzyme production (Levin et al., 2010).

1.2.2 Effect of incubation time on enzyme production

The effect of incubation time on enzyme production is a well-studied topic in biotechnology. Incubation time is a crucial factor in enzyme production, as it affects the growth of microorganisms and the production of enzymes. A study investigated the effect of incubation time on bacterial growth and enzyme production (Alrumman et al., 2018) and found out that the

incubation time had a significant effect on bacterial growth and enzyme production. The optimal incubation time for maximum enzyme production varied depending on the specific enzyme and microorganism being used.

Another study investigated the effect of incubation time on the activity of lipase produced by *Bacillus thuringiensis* on coconut dregs (Murtius et al., 2022). The study found that the incubation time had a significant effect on lipase activity, with the highest activity observed after 30 h of incubation. The effect of incubation time on alpha amylase activity (Zar, 2013) was reported to have a significant effect on alpha amylase activity, with the highest activity observed after 4 h of incubation. On this note, the optimal incubation time for enzyme production varies depending on the specific enzyme and microorganism being used. For example, in the case of fusaproliferin production by *Fusarium subglutinans* ITEM 2404, the optimal incubation period was 6 weeks at 20 °C. In the fermentation process of erythromycin production, the alkaline phosphatase activity and protein content decreased after the 7th day of incubation. In the production of cellulase using durian peel waste as substrates and *A. niger* as the secreting organism, the optimum cellulase production was 120 h of incubation, giving protein content of 0.3960% and enzyme activity of 1,069.01 ppm (Sukma et al., 2014). Therefore, it is important to determine the optimum incubation time for each specific enzyme and microorganism to achieve maximum enzyme production.

1.2.3 Temperature Effect on Enzyme Activity

Temperature significantly impacts enzyme activity. As temperature rises, enzyme activity generally increases up to an optimal temperature, enhancing reaction rates. However, excessive heat can denature enzymes, altering their structure and rendering them inactive (Andria et al., 2023). Each enzyme has an optimal temperature range for maximal activity, typically around 37

°C, with variations for different enzymes adapted to specific temperature ranges (Md Fauzul et al., 2023). The kinetic energy of molecules increases with temperature, leading to more collisions and faster reactions, but excessive heat can disrupt enzyme structure, reducing activity (Peterson et al. 2007). According to AAT Bioquest (2024), the optimal temperature for enzyme activity is typically between 20 °C and 30 °C, where enzyme activity is highest due to the conducive kinetic energy for maximum collisions between enzyme and substrate molecules.

1.2.4 Substrate Concentration Effect on Enzyme Activity

Substrate concentration affects the maximum degree of hydrolysis by influencing the rate of the enzymatic reaction. Initially, as substrate concentration increases, the rate of reaction also increases until the enzyme becomes saturated with substrate, reaching its maximum rate of reaction, V_{max} . At low substrate concentrations, the rate of reaction is limited by the availability of substrate, leading to a steep increase in reaction rate with increasing substrate concentration. However, once the enzyme is saturated, adding more substrate does not significantly affect the rate of reaction. The relationship between rate of reaction and substrate concentration is crucial for understanding enzyme kinetics and determining factors like K_m and V_{max} .

According to AAT Bioquest (2023), high substrate concentration can lead to substrate inhibition, where the enzyme's active sites become saturated with substrate molecules, causing a decrease in enzyme activity. This inhibition occurs because at high substrate concentrations, the enzyme is overwhelmed with substrate molecules, leading to a reduction in the rate of enzymatic reaction despite the surplus of substrate available (Shijie, 2017).

1.3 Applications of cellulase

Cellulases are enzymes that break down cellulose, a complex carbohydrate, into simpler sugars. They have various applications in different industries, including food, feed, and beverage industries. In the food industry, cellulases are used for tenderizing fruits, clarifying fruit juices, extracting flavoring materials and essential oils, improving the filterability of vanilla extracts, and enhancing the aroma and taste of food items. In the feed industry, cellulases improve the nutritional value of feed and animal health by breaking down plant cell wall polysaccharides into digestible components (Kumar et al., 2019).

In the wine industry, cellulases are used for alcohol production by converting cellulosic biomass to fermentable sugars, which are then converted to alcohol by yeast (Ramesh et al., 2011). The use of cellulases in wine making offers many advantages, such as quality and stability of wine, clarification, better color development, and improved maceration. Cellulases reduce the wort viscosity and enhance the aroma of wines by hydrolyzing glycosylated precursors into glucose and aroma compounds (Kumar et al., 2019).

In the olive oil extraction process, cellulases are used for the extraction of oil from olives. They help in breaking down the cell walls of olives, releasing the oil trapped inside. Cellulases are also used in the textile industry for biostoning of jeans, biopolishing of textile fibers, improving fabrics quality, and removing excess dye from fabrics (Ramesh et al., 2011). In the pulp and paper industry, cellulases are used as co-additives in pulp bleaching, biomechanical pulping, improved draining, enzymatic deinking, reduced energy requirement, reduced chlorine requirement, improved fiber brightness, strength properties, and pulp freeness and cleanliness, improved drainage in paper mills, and production of biodegradable cardboard, paper towels, and sanitary paper (Gupta et al., 2013). In the biofuel production industry, cellulases are used for

converting cellulosic materials to ethanol, other solvents, organic acids, and single-cell protein and lipids, and producing energy-rich animal feed. In the detergent industry, cellulase-based detergents provide superior cleaning action without damaging fibers, improved color brightness and dirt removal, removal of rough protuberances in cotton fabrics, and anti redeposition of ink particles (Ramesh et al., 2011).

In summary, cellulases have various applications in different industries, including food, feed, and beverage, wine, olive oil extraction, textile, pulp and paper, biofuel production, and detergent industries. They help in improving the quality, efficiency, and sustainability of various industrial processes.

1.4 Aim and Specific Objectives

1.4.1 Aim of the Study

The aim of the study was to understand the kinetics and biochemical characterization of cellulase from *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives

The objectives of this study were to:

1. determine the effect of incubation time on production of cellulase
2. determine the optimum pH required for cellulase production
3. ascertain the effect of nitrogen sources on cellulase production
4. investigate the effect of pH and temperature conditions on cellulase activity

5. estimate the kinetic parameters of the enzyme, including the Michealis constant (K_m) and the maximum rate of reaction (V_{max}).

CHAPTER TWO

MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

2.1.1 Collection of sample

Cassava effluent used in this research study was gotten from Orba road in Nsukka Local Government of Enugu State. Cassava effluent was obtained from a garri processing site. The Cassava effluent was preserved in a closed plastic container.

FIGURE 2.1 Cassava effluent

2.1.2 Chemicals

All chemicals used in this research were obtained from Jechoem and were of analytical grade. absolute ethanol, peptone, 3, 5-dinitrosalicylic acid (DNSA), acidified potassium dichromate (vi)

solution chromate reagent), sodium hydroxide, concentrated sulfuric acid, sodium potassium tartarate, yeast extract, pentose dextrose agar (PDA), hydrochloric acid, ammonium sulphate, sodium nitrite, meat extract, iron (ii) sulphate, magnesium sulphate, distilled water.

2.1.3 Equipment and apparatus

The following equipment/apparatus were used to carry out the experiment

Equipment/Apparatus	Manufacturer
Centrifuge	ARI, China
Water bath	Wincom Ltd, China
Spectrophotometer	Surgicare, England
Magnetic stirrer	PEC Medical, USA
Electronic balance	AMIS, China
Bunsen burner	Biobase, China
Gas cylinder	Tianlong, China
Refrigerator	Electrolux, Sweden
Incubator	Analytik Jena, USA
pH meter	Polycase, USA
Syringes	JSMC, Nigeria
Beaker	Pyrex, England
Test tubes	Gallenkamp, England

Hot plate	Smart houseware,
China	
Cork borer	Zoom, India
Flat bottom conical flask	Pyrex, Germany
Measuring cylinder	Pyrex, Germany
Air tight containers	Nakpo plastic,
Nigeria	
Nylon	Flash consult,
Nigeria	
Filter paper	Bossa, Nigeria
Petri dishes	FDCELL, Europe
Wire loop	Cerclage, India
Masking tape	Benoly Co. Ltd,
Nigeria	
Micropipette	Perfect, England
Foil paper	HTMM, China
Distilled water	Chem Dept, UNN

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Culturing

A known quantity (11.7 g) of PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar) was weighed into a conical flask and dissolved with 200 mL of distilled water. The mixture was stirred and shaken well for proper

dilution. 100 mL of distilled water was added into the solution and diluted properly. The solution was divided into two beakers, corked and then sterilized using pressure pot/autoclave for 30 mins. After the stipulated time, the sterilized agar was removed and allowed to cool at room temperature. The cooled agar was poured into 10 petri dishes and left to gel. Three test tubes were sterilized. In test tube 1, 10 mL of distilled water was measured and three loops of cassava effluent was transferred into it. It was dissolved properly and streaked on three petri dishes. Test tube 2 contained 10 mL of distilled water and two loops of cassava effluent was transferred into it. It was properly shaken and streaked on three petri dishes. Test tube 3 contained 9 mL of distilled water and 1 mL of the substrate from test tube 1. It was properly dissolved and streaked on another three petri dishes. The cassava effluent was streaked directly on the remaining petri dish. All 10 petri dishes were labeled properly and preserved in an enclosed place to avoid contamination. The growth of microorganism is closely monitored.

2.2.2 Sub-culturing

After microorganism growth has been noticed, sub-culturing is done to get a particular strain of the microorganism. Another media was prepared using PDA and sterilized. The mixture was poured into 8 petri dish and allowed to gel. A strain of microbe from the cultured media was inoculated into the newly prepared media.

2.3 Production of cellulase

2.3.1 Preparation of fermentation broth for cellulase production

The fermentation broth is made up of the following mixture; 3 g of $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$, 6 g of KH_2PO_4 , 1 g of MgSO_4 , 0.1 g of FeSO_4 , 20 g carboxymethyl cellulose and 0.5 g peptone. These chemicals

were dissolved in 1000 mL of distilled water and divided into 10 conical flasks. The mixture was sterilized for 10 mins using pressure pot. After the sterilization, it was allowed to cool and six corking of the microorganisms was inoculated into each of the 10 conical flasks. 10 days optimization began properly.

2.3.2 Harvesting of cellulase

On each stipulated day, the broth is centrifuged for 10 mins. The supernatant is collected and refrigerated

2.3.3 Effect of incubation time on cellulase production

After the 10 days optimization, the supernatant were removed from the refrigerator and allowed to cool. To test for the effect of incubation time on cellulase production, the following experiment was carried out. To prepare the substrate blank 0.5 mL of buffer, 0.5 mL of the freezed cellulase (day 1 - day 10) and 0.5 mL of H₂O are transferred into 10 labelled test tubes. To prepare the enzyme blank 0.5 mL of buffer, 0.5 mL of substrate (20% carboxymethyl cellulase) and 0.5 mL of H₂O are transferred into just 1 test tube. For the main test, 0.5 mL of buffer, 0.5 mL of the freezed cellulase (day 1 - day 10) and 0.5 mL of substrate (20% carboxymethyl cellulase) are transferred into another 10 labelled test tubes. The absorbance is read for all the test tubes.

2.3.4 Effect of pH on cellulase production

To evaluate the effect of pH on cellulase production, the pH of each hydrolysate was varied ranging from 4-12 at interval of 1. The pH of the medium was adjusted by using 1 N HCl or 1 N

NaOH. The standardized inoculum was then introduced into various flasks and fermented for a duration that resulted in maximum ethanol production. At the end of the fermentation duration, cellulase yield was determined, and the pH that gave the highest yield in cellulase was chosen for further experiments.

2.3.5 Effect of nitrogen source on cellulase production

Various nitrogen sources (3 g) (peptone, ammonium sulphate, sodium nitrite, and meat extract) were added to 4 different conical flasks. 6 g of NaHPO₄, 1 g of MgSO₄, 0.1 g FeSO₄, 20 g of carboxymethyl cellulase in its dissolved form were measured each into all 4 conical flasks. The mixtures were sterilized for 10 mins. The flasks were inoculated with 6 corks of freshly cultured microbial isolate. This experiment is carried out to know which nitrogen sources gives us better yield.

2.4 Purification of cellulase

2.4.1 Gel filtration/Column chromatography

Gel filtration is a separation technique based on the principle of size exclusion. The higher molecular weight leaves the gel column through the excluded volume and is released first, while the smaller molecular weight permeates through the gel and elutes last unlike gel electrophoresis in which the higher molecular weight leaves last and the smaller one leaves first.

For this procedure, Sephadex G-200 was used as the gel. Tris buffer was also prepared at pH 10.5. The gel and buffer were packed into the gel column and allowed to pack properly. The gel

was poured into the column using a glass rod. The tris buffer kept dropping as the gel was packing, so the column was refilled with buffer at intervals. After properly packing the gel, cellulase is gently added down the column side by side. EDTA bottle was placed under the column and the partially purified enzyme was allowed to drop down into it. Once it reached 5 mL, the time it took was recorded and another EDTA bottle was placed and timed at every 5 mL. Whenever the enzyme in the column got close to the packed gel, it was quickly replaced by more of buffer while the enzyme permeated the gel after the buffer was added. In this separation technique, the gel was the stationary phase and the buffer was the mobile phase. This was done in order to get a clear filtrate of cellulase.

2.5 Characterization of cellulase

2.5.1 Effect of pH on cellulase activity

Buffer is prepared for this experiment. Fermentation broth for cellulase was prepared with the chemicals used before and dissolved in 1000 mL of distilled water. The mixture was divided into 2 beakers. 1 N (normal) HCL was used to adjust the pH of the first half of the broth to pH 4, pH 5, pH 6 and pH 7. 5% NaOH was used to adjust the pH of the other half of the fermentation broth to pH 8, pH 9, pH 10, pH 11 and pH 12. 100 mL of each of the solution with adjusted pH was poured into labelled conical flask and corked. The mixture was sterilized in the pressure pot and allowed to cool.

2.5.2 Effect of Temperature on cellulase activity

A 0.5 mL buffer of 4.5 pH was prepared. The prepared buffer was reacted with 0.5 mL of carboxymethyl cellulose and 0.5 mL of cellulase. 7 test-tubes were labelled from 30 °C to 90 °C. Read the labelled test-tubes at their individual temperature for 20 mins. 1 mL of DNSA was added into all 7 test-tubes and they were boiled for 10 mins. After cooling, Na-K⁺ tartarate. Then absorbance is read. The aim of this reaction is to know at what temperature cellulase has the highest activity.

2.5.3 Effect of substrate concentration on cellulase activity

Test tubes were labelled from 1- 10 accordingly. In test tube 1, 0.1 mL carboxymethyl cellulose, 0.9 mL of buffer (4.5 pH), were measured. In test tube 2, 0.2 mL carboxymethyl cellulose, 0.8mL of buffer (4.5 pH) were measured. In test tube 3, 0.3 mL of carboxymethyl cellulose, 0.7 mL of buffer (4.5 pH) were measured. In test tube 4, 0.4 mL of carboxymethyl cellulose, 0.6 mL of buffer (4.5 pH) were measured. In test tube 5, 0.5 mL of carboxymethyl cellulose, 0.5 mL of buffer (4.5 pH) were measured. In test tube 6, 0.6 mL of carboxymethyl cellulose, 0.4 mL of buffer (4.5 pH) were measured. In test tube 7, 0.7 mL of carboxymethyl cellulose, 0.3 mL of buffer (4.5 pH) were measured. In test tube 8, 0.8 mL of carboxymethyl cellulose, 0.2 mL of buffer (4.5 pH) were measured. In test tube 9, 0.9 mL of carboxymethyl cellulose, 0.1 mL of buffer (4.5 pH) were measured. In test tube 10, only 1.0 mL of carboxymethyl cellulose was measured. 0.5 mL of buffer and 0.5mL of cellulase was added into all the 10 test tubes. All 10 test tubes are then incubated at a temperature of 60 °C for 20 mins. After incubating, 1 mL of DNSA is added immediately to all test tubes. The mixture was boiled again for 10 mins and

sodium tartarate was added to all 10 test tubes before reading absorbance. This helps to calculate the K_m and V_{max} .

V_{max} is the maximum reaction velocity at which all enzymes become saturated with substrate.

K_m is the substrate concentration at which half of the maximum velocity is achieved.

K_m and V_{max} are determined by incubating the enzyme with varying concentrations of substrate; the results can be plotted as a graph of rate of reaction (v) against concentration of substrate ($[S]$), and will normally yield a hyperbolic curve.

The relationship is defined by the Michaelis-Menten equation:

$$v = V_{max} / (1 + (K_m/[S]))$$

It is difficult to fit the best hyperbola through the experimental points, and difficult to determine V_{max} with any precision by estimating the limit of the hyperbola at infinite substrate concentration. A number of ways of re-arranging the Michaelis-Menten equation have been devised to obtain linear relationships which permit more precise fitting to the experimental points, and estimation of the values of K_m and V_{max} . One of the methods of this rearrangement is the Lineweaver-Burk plot.

The Lineweaver-Burk double reciprocal plot rearranges the Michaelis-Menten equation as:

$$1/v = 1/V_{max} + K_m/V_{max} \times 1/[S]$$

plotting $1/v$ against $1/[S]$ give a straight line:

$$y \text{ intercept} = 1/V_{max}$$

$$\text{gradient} = K_m/V_{max}$$

$$x \text{ intercept} = -1/K_m$$

2.6 Molecular characterization

2.6.1 DNA Extraction Using Zr Fungal/Bacterial DNA Miniprep (Manufactured by Zymo Research)

Add 2 mL of bacterial cells broth to a ZR Bashing™ Lysis Tube. Add 750 ul Lysis Solution to the tube. Secure in a bead fitted with 2 mL tube holder assembly and process at maximum speed for > 5 minutes. Centrifuge the ZR BashingBead™ Lysis Tube in a microcentrifuge at > 10,000 x g for 1 minute. Transfer up to 400 ul supernatant to a Zymo-Spin™ IV Spin Filter (orange top) in a Collection Tube and centrifuge at 7,000 x g for 1 min. Add 1,200 uL of Fungal/Bacterial DNA Binding Buffer to the filtrate in the Collection Tube from Step 4. Transfer 800 uL of the mixture from Step 5 to a Zymo-Spin™ IIC Column in a Collection Tube and centrifuge at 10,000 x g for 1 min. Discard the flow through from the Collection Tube and repeat Step 6. Add 200 ul DNA Pre-Wash Buffer to the Zymo-Spin™ IIC Column in new Collection Tube and centrifuge at 10,000 x g for 1 minute. Add 500 ul Fungal/Bacterial DNA Wash Buffer to the Zymo-Spin™ IIC Column and centrifuge at 10,000 x g for 1 min. Transfer the Zymo-Spin™ IIC Column to a clean 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube and add 100 uL (35 uL minimum) DNA Elution Buffer directly to the column matrix. Centrifuge at 10,000 x g for 30 secs to elute the DNA.

2.6.2 Electrophoresis for DNA and PCR

Measure 1 g of agarose (for DNA); 2 g of agarose for PCR. Mix agarose powder with 100 mL 1xTAE in a microwavable flask. Microwave for 1-3 mins until the agarose is completely dissolved (but do not over boil the solution, as some of the buffer will evaporate and thus alter the final percentage of agarose in the gel. Let agarose solution cool down to about 50 °C (about when you can comfortably keep your hand on the flask), about 5 mins. Add 10µL EZ vision DNA stain. EZ vision binds to the DNA and allows you to visualize the DNA under ultraviolet (UV) light. Pour the agarose into a gel tray with the well comb in place. Place newly poured gel at 4 °C for 10-15 mins OR let sit at room temperature for 20-30 mins, until it has completely solidified.

2.6.3 Loading Samples and Running an Agarose Gel

Add loading buffer to each of your DNA samples or PCR products. Once solidified, place the agarose gel into the gel box (electrophoresis unit). Fill gel box with 1xTAE (or TBE) until the gel is covered. Carefully load a molecular weight ladder into the first lane of the gel. Carefully load your samples into the additional wells of the gel. Run the gel at 80-150 V for about 1-1.5 h. Turn OFF power, disconnect the electrodes from the power source, and then carefully remove the gel from the gel box. Visualize DNA fragments or PCR product under UV transilluminator.

CHAPTER THREE

RESULTS

3.1 Isolation of Organism

Cassava effluent site (RHS) where the sample used for the isolation of the microorganism was collected. The plate 1 showed the pure culture of *P. kudriavzevii*

PLATE 3.1 Pure isolate of *P. kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190

3.2 Molecular characterization of *P. kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190

3.2.1 Gel electrophoresis band of *P. kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190

Lane M serves as the control of the DNA ladder which ranges from 50bp to 1350bp while lane 15_02=F12_ITS3 serves as the target organism with a total bp of 513

3.2.2 DNA sequencing of *P. kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190

The DNA sequence of *P. kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 after sequencing an amplification using polymerase chain reaction showed a total of 513bp which is equivalent to 1026 nucleotides. F12_ITS3 has 81.89% pairwise similarity with *Pichia kudriavzevii* strain AUMC 10190 which has NCBI accession number KU095862.1

**CATATGCCTCCGCTCTGTGCGTGAGCGACKTTTGTGWCACCT
ACAATGGGKCTATAGGTATGGTCGATGGAAAAATGTAAGATCG
CTCGRCAGCTTTCACCATTTAAGGCGAGGCGCTCTCCGACGCT
CTTTACACGYCGTCCGCTCCGCTCCCCCAACTCTGCGCACGCS
CAWGAWGCAWCCCCCGCTCGAACAGGCATGCCCCCGKAA
TGCCGMGGGGSGSRATGKGC GTTCTAGAACTCGATGAYTCAC
GAYGSCTGCAATTCAYACTAGGWATCGCATTTCGCTGCGCTC
TTCATCGATGCGAGAWCCAAKAGAYCYGWTGTTGAMAGWTT
TGTTTGTTTTTTCSTARAYTTCTTTTGWCGACYATATGCTATATT**

CCACAWTTTAKGYGTTGWTGYMTTCAATCCGCTCYCSCATYR
KWGTACTAAATCCCMGTAAAYGTTTCCTTCCGCAGGATCSCGCT
AAAGAA

3.2.3 Taxonomy and phylogenetic tree of *P. kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190

The phylogenetic tree of *P. kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 showed close similarity in the DNA nucleotide sequence of similar organism of different and unique strain. *P. kudriavzevii* strain PK12, *P. sp.* QAUPK03, *P. kudriavzevii* strain ITD-2MA-94 had the closest similarity up to 80%.

FIGURE 3. 1: (a) High molecular weight extracted from isolate lane 15_02=F12 ITS

(b) Gel image showing amplification of the internal Transcribe Spacer (ITS) of

the isolate. Lane M is a 50bp DNA ladder, lane 15_02=F12_ITS3

FIGURE 3.2: Taxonomy of *P. kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190

3.3 Production of cellulase

3.3.1 Effect of incubation time on production of cellulase

Submerged fermentation was carried out for 10 days to determine the day(s) of highest cellulase yield. Carboxymethyl cellulose (2%) was used as substrates. The highest cellulase activity and protein was obtained on day 1. Day 1 was chosen to be used for enzyme loading.

3.3.2 Effect of pH on cellulase production

The optimum pH values for cellulase from *P. kudravzeii* was found to be 5.0 as shown in the figure below.

3.3.3 Effect of nitrogen sources on cellulase production

Nitrogen sources serves as one of the inducers for cellulase production. Meat extract, peptone, sodium nitrite and ammonium sulphate are the nitrogen sources used in this experiment. Meat extract was the best nitrogen source that gave the highest production of cellulase, followed by sodium nitrite, peptone and ammonium sulphate was the least inducer for cellulase.

FIGURE 3.3: Effect of incubation period on cellulase production

FIGURE 3.4: Effect of pH on cellulase production

FIGURE 3.5: Effect of Nitrogen source on cellulase production

3.4 Purification of cellulase

3.4.1 Gel filtration chromatography profile

Following, gel permeation chromatography, the purification profile in terms of specific activity, fold purification and % yield are shown in the Table 1. The enzyme was purified up to 2 folds with the yield of 59% and specific activity of 1141.3 U/mg. The partial purified cellulase was observed to be active over a wide range of pH from 4.0 to 12.0. The activity of cellulase present in crude culture medium produced by *Pichia kudriavzevii* strain AUMC 10190 was determined and was found to be 446.3 U. The flow rate was 13.9 mL per hour.

3.4.2 Summary of purification table

The crude enzyme was purified in a single step purification using Gel filtration chromatography Sephadex G-200 with specific activity after purification increase from 294.5 to 1141.3 U/mg and the protein content dropped from 0.66 to 0.23 mg/mL.

FIGURE 3.6: Gel filtration profile

TABLE 3.1: Purification table of cellulase

Purification Step	Activity (U)	Protein (mg/mL)	Specific (U/mg)	Activity	Yield (%)	Fold
Crude Enzyme	446.3	0.66	294.5		100	1
Sephadex G-200	262.5	0.23	1141.3		59	2

3.5 Cellulase characterization

3.5.1 Effect of pH on cellulase activity

The purified cellulase of *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 was relatively stable in the pH range of 3.5 to 8.0. Cellulase activity increased significantly from pH 3.5 to 4.0. Cellulase activity gradually increases and declines as the pH level increases. The optimal pH for cellulase activity is recorded as pH 4.5, with activity of 172.667 U, just surpassing pH 4.0, which has activity of 171.5U.

3.5.2 Effect of temperature on cellulase activity

The graphic below shows that cellulase activity gradually increases from 40 to 60 °C. This is obvious from the statistics, which shows that activity increased from 67.667 to 191.333 U. As the temperature rises from 60 to 70 °C, the activity increases significantly from 191.333 to 1774.5 units. At 80 °C, the value drops significantly to 253.75 units. This could be due to the enzyme's denaturation. The activity of cellulase peaks at 70 °C.

3.5.3 Effect of substrate concentration on cellulase activity

The plot indicates a significant rise in cellulase activity as the substrate concentration increases from 0 to 0.1. The activity of cellulase steadily increases when the substrate concentration rises to 0.6. The maximal activity is measured at substrate concentrations of 0.5.

FIGURE 3.7: Effect of pH on cellulase activity

FIGURE 3.8: Effect of Temperature on cellulase activity

FIGURE 3.9: Effect of substrate concentration on cellulase activity

$K_m = 0.018868$ $V_{max} = 188.6792$

FIGURE 3.10: Lineweaver-burk plot of substrate concentration in cellulose

CHAPTER FOUR

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

4.1 Discussion

Fungal isolates were obtained from a sample of cassava effluent by serial dilution using potato dextrose agar (PDA) as an isolation medium. The isolates were subcultured and recultured on PDA to obtain pure fungal isolates. The pure cultures were then subjected to biochemical screening and identified as *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190. Submerged fermentation system was carried out in cellulase production using the yeast strain, *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 and this showed that the organism produced maximum cellulase on day 1 during the optimization process from day 1 to day 10. This agrees with the work of Maidul et al. (2019), which reported a maximum cellulase activity after 24 h (day 1) using *Bacillus sp.* This is in contrast to the study done by Merlin et al. (2024) on *Pichia kudriavzevii* SVMS2019 which states that *Pichia kudriavzevii* SVMS2019 had a maximal cellulase activity of after 72 h of incubation, which confirmed their activity. In a similar research conducted by Sajib et al. (2021) cellulase production by *Bacillus pseudomycoides* observed the maximum cellulose activity after 72 h (day 3). This suggests that an early-fermentation period might be common for peak cellulase production regardless of organism (*Bacillus* or *Pichia*) or strain (*Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 or *Pichia kudriavzevii* SVMS2019).

Following an amplification using the polymerase chain reaction, the DNA sequence of *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 revealed a total of 513 bp, or 1026 nucleotides. *Pichia kudriavzevii* strains obtained from various sources had their internal transcribed spacer (ITS) amplified and sequenced by Wang et al. (2010). Their sequences varied from 530 to 550 bp, which equates to

around 1060 to 1100 nucleotides. In another comparable investigation, Naumov et al. (2017) revealed a variety of genome sizes among *Pichia kudriavzevii*, with some strains reaching 12 million bp. These vast ranges show the possibility for large diversity in genome size despite similarity in specific amplified areas and genome could demonstrate some amount of size conservation between strains.

The effect of pH on the production of cellulase was monitored between the pH range of 4 – 12. It showed that *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 could produce maximum cellulase at pH 5.0. However, this was different with the work of Maidul et al. (2019) which reported maximum cellulase production at pH 3.5 using *Bacillus sp.* Also, according to Weldesemayat & Tesfaye (2014), the optimal pH was 5.5 for all seven isolates of *Trichoderma sp.* The *P. kudriavzevii* SVMS2019 showed a wide range of pH tolerance (pH 4 to pH 8), but a maximum cellulase production was achieved at pH 6.0 (Merlin et al. 2024). pH environment influence the metabolic process of an organism in activating different factors or biomolecules.

The effect of nitrogen sources on the production of cellulase was also measured as it has a significant influence on the metabolic process of microorganism in the production of biological molecules. Peptone, meat extract, sodium nitrite and ammonium sulphate were used in this study. Meat extract was the best nitrogen source that gave the highest production of cellulase, followed by sodium nitrite, peptone with ammonium sulphate as the least inducer for cellulase. In a similar research, Datsomor et al. (2022) reported that yeast recorded significantly the highest cellulase activity (1.354 U/mL) compared to other nitrogen sources when investigating *Pleurotus ostreatus* and *Phanerochaete chrysosporium*. Karthikeyan et al. (2011) observed that cellulase activity reached the peak value when ammonium nitrate was the sole nitrogen source as ammonium nitrate was good for cellulase synthesis in their work with *Penicillium sp.* Similarly,

Weldesemayat & Tesfaye (2014) observed that all *Trichoderma* isolates on yeast extract medium showed the highest cellulase production whereas on sodium nitrate medium showed the least cellulase production. This highlights the potential influence of the microorganism on nitrogen source preference.

The crude enzyme was purified in a single step purification using Gel filtration chromatography Sephadex G-200 with specific activity after purification increase from 294.5 to 1141.3 U/mg and the protein content dropped from 0.66 to 0.23 mg/mL. The enzyme was purified up to 2 folds with the yield of 59%. According to the study done by Okonkwo (2014), after the purification of the crude cellulase using Sephadex G-200 the specific activity increased from 0.2 U/mg to 4.00 U/mg, the protein content dropped from 12.50 mg/mL to 1.20 mg/mL with a purification fold of 20 and percentage yield of 4.9. Ozioko et al. (2013) purified cellulase isolated from *Achatina achatina* up to 55.49 folds with a yield of 2.7%. It showed a specific activity of 347.34 U/mg and protein content of 0.47 mg/mL.

The purified cellulase of *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 was highly stable in the pH range of 3 – 8 with optimum pH recorded as pH 4.5, with activity of 172.667 U. However, according to Maidul et al. (2019) it was said that the enzyme activity started increasing from pH 4.5 and the maximum activity was found at pH 5 in the research carried out using *Bacillus sp.* In a similar research by Ozioko et al. (2013) using *Achatina achatina*, it was discovered that the pH optima for total cellulase activity was 5.5. Weldesemayat & Tesfaye (2014) observed that the maximum enzymatic activity of cellulase was obtained at pH range 4.7– 5.4 with optimum pH at 5 for all *Trichoderma isolates*. *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 was grown under specific culture conditions which highlights the influence of factors like growth media composition, fermentation

parameters, and purification techniques on the final enzyme activity. It is important to note however that cellulase activity can vary significantly depending on several factors.

Cellulase of *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 was active in the temperature range of 40 to 60 °C. The results showed increased activity from 67.667 U to 191.333 U. As the temperature rose from 60 to 70 °C, the activity increased significantly from 191.333 to 1774.5 U. At 80 °C, the value dropped to 253.75 U. This could be due to the enzyme's denaturation. In this study, the optimum temperature was 70 °C. This is in contrast to the work done by Maidul et al. (2019) who reported maximum cellulase activity at 50 °C using *Bacillus sp.* The enzyme activity increased with temperature within the range of 40 - 60 °C similar to the cellulase of *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190. Ozioko et al. (2013) observed the maximum cellulase activity at a temperature of 50 °C while working with African giant snail (*Achatina achatina*).

The variations amongst the different tests were mostly due to the difference in fungal strain and method of cellulase production. The activity of cellulase steadily increases when the substrate concentration rises to 0.6. The highest activity is measured at substrate concentrations of 0.5. Okonkwo (2014) however observed that the highest activity was found at 1 % concentration in all the substrates. In a research work by Bhatia et al. (2017), it was observed that the effect of substrate concentration on cellulase activity was studied using various concentrations (0.5% to 5%) of CMC. Highest cellulase activity for wild strain was recorded with 1% CMC.

Lineweaver–Burk double reciprocal plot was used for the analysis of V_{max} and K_m values. The total cellulase showed a maximum velocity, V_{max} , of 188.6792 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}$ and a Michaelis-Menten constant, K_m , of 0.018868 mg cellulase.

4.2 Conclusion

The results from this study have indicated that *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 is capable of producing high activities of cellulase. The optimum pH for cellulase enzyme production from *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 was 5.0. Meat extract was the preferred nitrogen source to produce cellulase. The optimum temperature and pH for cellulase enzyme activity from *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 were 70° C and 4.5 respectively. Moreover, it may be concluded that the adaptability of *Pichia kudriavzevii* AUMC 10190 to a wide range of temperatures and pH for its growth and cellulolytic activity, strongly indicates that this may be grown in various habitats with different environmental conditions of pH and temperature and can play an important role in cellulose degradation for sustainable development. It will not only help in the production of useful end products including bioethanol from the biodegradation of the low cost enormous stock of cellulose but also help in the disposal of cellulosic wastes which is continuously added to the environment.

4.3 Recommendation

It is imperative that significant effort made to manage the copious amounts of agricultural waste that Nigeria produces each year. By utilizing these wastes to produce cellulase, we can help solve the issue of waste disposal in the environment. More investigation is required to conduct a thorough chemical characterization in order to ascertain the influence of various substrates and their thermostability. Most importantly, more research should be carried out on ways to increase the yield of cellulase produced.

REFERENCES

AAT Bioquest. (n.d). What is the effect of substrate concentration on enzyme activity? Retrieved from <https://www.aatbio.com/resources/faq-frequently-asked-questions/what-is-the-effect-of-substrate-concentration-on-enzyme-activity>

AAT Bioquest. (n.d). What is the optimal temperature for enzymes? <https://www.aatbio.com/resources/faq-frequently-asked-questions/what-is-the-optimal-temperature-for-enzymes>

Alan, O. C., Estéfani, A. A., Pedro, F., Souza, F. & Everaldo, S. S. (2024). Extraction of Cellulases Produced through Solid-State Fermentation by *Trichoderma reesei* CCT-2768 Using Green Coconut Fibers Pretreated by Steam Explosion Combined with Alkali. *Biomass*, 4(1), 92-106; <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomass4010005>

Alrumman, S., Mostafa, Y., Al-Qahtani, S. & Taha, T. (2018). Hydrolytic Enzyme Production by Thermophilic Bacteria Isolated from Saudi Hot Springs. *Open Life Sciences*, 13, 470-480. <https://doi.org/10.1515/biol-2018-0056>.

Andria, E. & Sarah, P. (2023). Temperature & Enzyme Activity | Overview & Effect - Lesson <https://study.com/academy/lesson/effect-of-temperature-on-enzyme-activity.html>.

Bhatia, R.K., Kumar, R., Rathour, R.K., Kumar, V., Sharma, V., Rana, N., Thakur, S. & Bhatt, A. K. (2017). Enhancement of Cellulose Degradation Potential of *Bacillus sp.* Hcb-21 through Mutagenesis. *J Microb Biochem Technol*, 9(6), 257-265. <https://doi.org/10.4172/1948-5948.1000374>

Cellulase Enzymes Transform Industries: Textiles, Pulp and Paper, Food, and More, Driving Market Growth. (2023, September 21). Globe News Wire. <https://www.globenewswire.com/en/news-release/2023/09/21/2747290/28124/en/Cellulase-Enzymes-Transform-Industries-Textiles-Pulp-and-Paper-Food-and-More-Driving-Market-Growth.htm>

Cerda, A., Artola, A., Barrena, R., Font, X., Gea, T. & Sánchez, A. (2019). Innovative Production of Bioproducts From Organic Waste Through Solid-State Fermentation. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 3, 2571-581X, <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fsufs.2019.00063>

Chavda, N. R., Patel, P. H., & Chaudhary, R. K. (2023). Isolation and Production of Cellulase from Bacteria using agro waste. *Biotech Res Asia*, 20(4). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13005/bbra/3192>

Datsomor, O., Yan, Q., Opoku-Mensah, L., Zhao, G. & Miao, L. (2022). Effect of Different Inducer Sources on Cellulase Enzyme Production by White-Rot Basidiomycetes *Pleurotus ostreatus* and *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* under Submerged Fermentation. *Fermentation*. 8(10), 561. <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation8100561>.

do Nascimento, G. C., Batista, R. D., Santos, C. C. A. D. A., da Silva, E. M., de Paula, F. C., Mendes, D. B., de Oliveira, D. P., & de Almeida, A. F. (2019). β -Fructofuranosidase and β -D-Fructosyltransferase from New *Aspergillus carbonarius* PC-4 Strain Isolated from Canned Peach Syrup: Effect of Carbon and Nitrogen Sources on Enzyme Production. *The Scientific World Journal*, 6956202. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/6956202>

Ejaz, U., Sohail, M., & Ghanemi, A. (2021). Cellulases: From Bioactivity to a Variety of Industrial Applications. *Biomimetics (Basel, Switzerland)*, 6(3), 44. <https://doi.org/10.3390/biomimetics6030044>

Elsababty, Z. E., Abdel-Aziz, S. H., Ibrahim, A. M., Guirgis, A. A., & Dawwam, G. E. (2022). Purification, biochemical characterization, and molecular cloning of cellulase from *Bacillus licheniformis* strain Z9 isolated from soil. *Journal, genetic engineering & biotechnology*, 20(1), 34. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s43141-022-00317-4>

Garg, R., Srivastava, R., Brahma, V. Verma, L., Karthikeyan, S., Sahni, G. (2016). Biochemical and structural characterization of a novel halotolerant cellulase from soil metagenome. *Sci Rep* 6, 39634. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep39634>

Gaur, R. & Tiwari, S. (2015). Isolation, production, purification and characterization of an organic-solvent-thermostable alkalophilic cellulase from *Bacillus vallismortis* RG-07. *BMC Biotechnol* 15, 19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12896-015-0129-9>

Gupta, R., Mehta, G., Deswal, D., Sharma, S., Jain, K., Kuhad, R. & Singh, A. (2013). Cellulases and Their Biotechnological Applications. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-81-322-0876-1_6.

Islam, F. & Roy, N. (2018). Screening, purification and characterization of cellulase from cellulase producing bacteria in molasses. *BMC Res Notes*, 11, 445 . <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13104-018-3558-4>

Karthikeyan, N., Sakthivel M., & Palani P. (2011). Screening, Identifying of *Penicillium* K-P Strain and Its Cellulase Producing Conditions. *Journal of Ecobiotechnology*, 2(10), 4-7, ISSN 2077-0464.

Kumar, V., Anoop & Kurup, S., Snishamol, C. & Prabhu, G. (2019). Role of Cellulases in Food, Feed, and Beverage Industries: Enzymes in Industrial Food Processing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-3263-0_17.

Kumari, P., Sayas, T., Bucki, P., Brown-Miyara, S. & Kleiman, M. (2020). Real-Time Visualization of Cellulase Activity by Microorganisms on Surface. *Int. J. Mol. Sci*, 21, 6593. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21186593>

Lesetja, M. L., Danie C. L. G. & Elbert L. J. R. (2023). Production of the Cellulase Enzyme System by Locally Isolated *Trichoderma* and *Aspergillus* Species Cultivated on Banana Pseudostem during Solid-State Fermentation. *Fermentation*, 9(5), 412; <https://doi.org/10.3390/fermentation9050412>

Levin, L., Melignani, E., & Ramos, A. M. (2010). Effect of nitrogen sources and vitamins on ligninolytic enzyme production by some white-rot fungi. Dye decolorization by selected culture filtrates. *Bioresource technology*, 101(12), 4554–4563. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2010.01.102>

Lizardi-Jiménez, M. A., & Hernández-Martínez, R. (2017). Solid state fermentation (SSF): diversity of applications to valorize waste and biomass. *Biotech*, 7(1), 44. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-017-0692-y>

Maidul, I., Palash, K. S. & Mohiuddin, A. K. M. (2019). Optimization of fermentation condition for cellulase enzyme production from *Bacillus sp.* *Malaysian Journal of Halal Research*, 2(2). DOI: 10.2478/mjhr-2019-0009.

Malik, W. A. & Javed, S. (2021). Biochemical Characterization of Cellulase From *Bacillus subtilis* Strain and its Effect on Digestibility and Structural Modifications of Lignocellulose Rich Biomass. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*. 9(0). ISSN=2296-4185 <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fbioe.2021.800265> DOI.10.3389/fbioe.2021.80 0265

Manan, M. A. & Webb, C. (2017). Design aspects of solid state fermentation as applied to microbial bioprocessing. *J Appl Biotechnol Bioeng*, 4(1), 511-532. DOI: 10.15406/jabb.2017.04.00094

Md Fauzul, K. & Lu-Kwang, J. (2023). On optimization of enzymatic processes: Temperature effects on activity and long-term deactivation kinetics. *Process Biochemistry*, 130, 734-746, ISSN 1359-5113. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procbio.2023.05.031>.

Megha, Maragathavalli, S. V., Brindha, S., Annadurai, V., Gangwar, S. K. & Karthikeyan, V. (2015). Isolation And Purification Of Cellulase. 6. 474-479.

Merlin, S. P., Iyyadurai, M., Krishnaveni, M. & Venkatesh, S. (2024). Insights of *Pichia kudriavzevii* SVMS2019 for cellulase production and fermentation into ethanol. *Renewable Energy*, 225, 120296, ISSN 0960-1481. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.120296>.

Murtius, W.S., Hari, P.D. & Putri, I.N. (2022). The Effect of Incubation Time to The Activity of Lipase Produced by *Bacillus thuringiensis* on Coconut (*Cocos nucifera* L.) Dregs. *IOP Conf.Ser.Earth Environ. Sci*, 1059, 012076. DOI 10.1088/1755-1315/1059/1/01206

Naumov, A., Kratzer, S., Ting, L. M., Kim, K., Suvorova E. S. & White, M. W. (2017). The *Toxoplasma* Centrocone Houses Cell Cycle Regulatory Factors. *mBio*, 8(4), e00579-17. <http://doi.org/10.1128/mBio.00579-17>.

Nicolás, O., Javier M.V., Antoni S., Edgar R. O. & Teresa G. (2022).Solid-State Fermentation from Organic Wastes: A New Generation of Bioproducts. *Processes*, 10(12), 2675. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr10122675>

Noor, T. H. & Hameed, M. J., (2018). Purification and Characterization of Cellulase enzyme from *Trichoderma longibrachiatum* isolated in Iraqi soil. *IOSR Journal of Biotechnology and Biochemistry (IOSR-JBB)*, 4(1), 32-41, ISSN: 2455-264X. www.iosrjournals.org.

Nóra, S., Zsófia, F., Kati, R., Miklós, M. & András, B. (2004). Cellulase fermentation on a novel substrate (waste cardboard) and subsequent utilization of home-produced cellulase and commercial amylase in a rabbit feeding trial. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 20(1), 49-57, ISSN 0926-6690. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2003.12.012>.

O'Fágáin, C., Cummins, P. M., & O'Connor, B. F. (2011). Gel-filtration chromatography. *Methods in molecular biology (Clifton, N.J.)*, 681, 25–33. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-60761-913-0_2

Okonkwo I. F. (2014). Effect of Substrate Concentration on the Activity of Cellulase Produced by *Aspergillus Flavus*. *Agriculture*, 4(7), ISSN – 2249-555X.

Ozioko, P. C., Eze, S. O. O. & Chilaka, F. C. (2013). Partial purification and characterization of cellulases from digestive tracts of the African giant snail (*Achatina achatina*). *Turk J Biol*, 37, 199-205. doi:10.3906/biy-1205-11.

Peterson, M. E., Daniel, R. M., Danson, M. J. & Eienthal, R. (2007). The dependence of enzyme activity on temperature: determination and validation of parameters. *The Biochemical journal*, 402(2), 331–337. <https://doi.org/10.1042/BJ20061143>

Praveen K. R. G., Narasimha G., Kanderi D. K., Ramanjaneyulu G. & Ramya A. (2015). Cellulase production by *Aspergillus niger* on different natural lignocellulosic substrates. *Int.J.Curr.Microbiol.App.Sci*, 4, 835-845.

Ramesh C. K., Rishi G. & Ajay S. (2011) Microbial Cellulases and Their Industrial Applications. *Enzyme Research*, 280696 <https://doi.org/10.4061/2011/280696>

Ricardo G. R. B., Livia da Silva C., Ninoska B. & Nei P. (2023). Endo-Exoglucanase Synergism for Cellulose Nanofibril Production Assessment and Characterization. *Molecules*, 28(3), 948; <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28030948>

Rodriguez-Couto, S. & Sanromán, M. (2006). Application of Solid-State Fermentation to Food Industry – a Review. *Journal of Food Engineering*. 76. 291-302. 10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2005.05.022.

Sajib, K. P., Shafi, M., Gobindo, K. P., Tabassum, J., Kamrun, N., Md. Salah, U., Shahriar Z. & Md. Abu S. (2021). Fermentation optimization of cellulase production from sugarcane bagasse by *Bacillus pseudomycooides* and molecular modeling study of cellulose. *Current research in Microbial Sciences*, 2(0),100013, ISSN: 2666-1574, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crmicr.2020.100013>

Sajith, S., Sreedevi, S. & Priji, P. (2014). Production and partial purification of cellulase from a novel fungus, *Aspergillus flavus* BS1. *Ann Microbiol* 64, 763–771. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13213-013-0711-0>

Sethi, S., Datta, A., Gupta, B. L., & Gupta, S. (2013). Optimization of cellulase production from bacteria isolated from soil. *ISRN biotechnology*, 985685. <https://doi.org/10.5402/2013/985685>

Sevakumaran, V., Lee, T., Bhubalan, K., & Amirul, A. A. (2015). Extracellular Polyhydroxyalkanoate Depolymerase by *Acidovorax* sp. DP5. *Enzyme Research*, 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/21-8>

Shijie L. (2017) Chapter 11 - How Cells Grow, *Bioprocess Engineering (Second Edition)*, Elsevier, pp 629-697, 9780444637833, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63783-3.00011-3>.

Sukma, B. A., Asmawit, A. & Pramono, P. U. (2014). Optimization of Incubation Time on Cellulase Enzyme Production Using *Aspergillus niger* Under Solid State Fermentation. *DOAJ*, 5(2). <https://doaj.org/article/8045e145b48d4dff93baa641f4d66c0c>

Sulyman, A.O., Igunnu, A. & Malomo, S.O. (2020). Isolation, purification and characterization of cellulase produced by *Aspergillus niger* cultured on *Arachis hypogaea* shells. *Heliyon*, 6(12), e05668, ISSN 2405-8440. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2020.e05668>.

Wang, J., Li, C., & Wang, E. (2010). Potential and flux landscapes quantify the stability and robustness of budding yeast cell cycle network. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 107(18), 8195–8200. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.09103311107>.

Weldesemayat, G. & Tesfaye, A. (2014). Production and optimization of cellulase from *Trichoderma isolates* under liquid state fermentation (LSF). *Ethiop. J. Sci.*, 37(2), 131–142, ISSN: 0379–2897

Wilson, D. B., & Kostylev, M. (2012). Cellulase processivity. *Methods in molecular biology (Clifton, N.J.)*, 908, 93–99. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-61779-956-3_9

Ye, M., Sun, L., Yang, R., Wang, Z., & Qi, K. (2017). The optimization of fermentation conditions for producing cellulase of *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* and its application to goose feed. *Royal Society open science*, 4(10), 171012. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.171012>

Zar, Dr. M. (2013). The influence of carbon and nitrogen supplementation on alpha amylase productivity of *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* IIB-14 using fuzzy-logic and two factorial designs. *African Journal of Microbiology Research*, 7, 120-129. <https://doi.org/10.5897/AJMR12.1519>